

THE INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND LEARNING INTEREST ON SOCIAL STUDIES LEARNING OUTCOMES OF NINTH GRADE STUDENTS AT SMP NEGERI 4 PEMATANGSIANTAR

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Received : 15 October 2025

Accepted : 20 November 2025

Revised : 01 November 2025

Published : 30 November 2025

Abstract

The problem in this study is the low learning outcomes of students in Social Studies subjects, which are presumed to be influenced by the family environment and low learning interest of ninth grade students at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar. This research is a quantitative study using a descriptive method. The population consisted of all ninth-grade students across 10 classes, totaling 319 students. The sample was determined using proportional random sampling, resulting in 80 respondents. Data were collected through questionnaires for the variables of family environment and learning interest, as well as documentation of Midterm Examination (UTS) scores in Social Studies as indicators of learning outcomes. The data analysis techniques employed included simple linear regression, multiple linear regression, t-test, F-test, and the coefficient of determination. The assumption test for analysis was conducted using the chi-square normality test, and the results indicated that both variables were normally distributed. The analysis showed that there is a positive and significant influence of the family environment on students' learning outcomes ($t_{count} = 3.43 > t_{table} = 1.664$) and a positive and significant influence of learning interest on students' learning outcomes ($t_{count} = 2.022 > t_{table} = 1.664$). The F-test results revealed that both variables simultaneously have a significant effect on students' learning outcomes ($F_{count} = 4.463 > F_{table} = 3.96$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.95574 indicates that 95.574% of the variation in students' learning outcomes is influenced by the family environment and learning interest, while the remaining 4.426% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

Keywords: *Family Environment, Learning Interest, Learning Outcomes*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and planned process designed to create a learning environment and process that enables students to optimally develop their potential. Through education, individuals are equipped with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary to face the changing times and challenges of life. Education also plays a strategic role in developing high-quality human resources with character and the ability to actively contribute to national development. Educational success is not solely determined by the learning process at school, but is also greatly influenced by various factors originating from within the students themselves and from their surrounding environment. One indicator of educational success in schools can be seen from student learning outcomes. Learning outcomes reflect the extent to which students are able to understand, master, and apply the material they have learned. Optimal learning outcomes indicate that the learning process is running effectively, while low learning outcomes indicate problems that require serious attention.

In the learning process, particularly in Social Studies (IPS), students are required not only to master theoretical concepts but also to understand social, economic, and cultural phenomena occurring in their environment. Social Studies plays a crucial role in shaping critical thinking, social attitudes, and student awareness as citizens. Therefore, low social studies learning outcomes are a problem that requires further study, as they can impact the quality of students' understanding of social life. One internal factor that significantly influences student learning success is interest in learning. Interest in learning is a tendency or drive within students characterized by a sense of enjoyment, attention, and a desire to actively participate in learning activities. Students with a strong interest in learning tend to be more focused in lessons, actively ask questions, diligently complete assignments, and are motivated to achieve higher levels of achievement. Conversely, students with a low interest in learning often

exhibit a passive attitude, lack enthusiasm, get bored easily, and make less effort to understand the material, which ultimately results in low learning outcomes. In addition to internal factors, external factors also have a significant influence on student learning success. One of the external factors most closely related to a child's life is the family environment. The family is the child's first and primary educational environment. From birth, children are exposed to various values, habits, and behavioral patterns from their families. Parents play a crucial role in providing attention, guidance, motivation, and adequate learning facilities. A harmonious, loving, and supportive family environment will help children feel emotionally secure and thus able to concentrate on their studies.

However, not all students grow up in ideal family environments. Differences in parenting styles, level of attention to their children's education, socioeconomic conditions, and the intensity of communication within the family can lead to variations in the learning support students receive. Lack of parental involvement, minimal supervision of technology use, and limited time for study support at home can hinder the development of students' learning interests. These conditions can ultimately impact low learning outcomes at school. Based on initial observations conducted by researchers at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar, it was found that students' social studies learning outcomes were still relatively low. Final Semester Exam data showed that the majority of students had not yet achieved the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) set by the school. Of the 319 eighth-grade students, only 116 students (57.14%) were declared to have completed the learning, while 203 students (42.86%) still did not reach the KKM. This percentage of incompleteness indicates that nearly half of the students still need improvement in learning outcomes, particularly in social studies.

Furthermore, preliminary interviews with several students revealed that their learning interests varied. Some students admitted to being less enthusiastic about social studies because they found the material difficult to understand or uninteresting. Furthermore, parental involvement in their children's learning process was also uneven. Some parents actively assisted their children in their studies, managed study time, and limited device use. However, others were less involved due to work commitments or a lack of awareness of the importance of the family's role in education. These findings were reinforced by observations of the family environment, which showed that although most parents provided learning resources, such as books and stationery, and accompanied their children's studies for approximately 1–2 hours per day, supervision of television and cell phone use was still suboptimal. The average student spent 3–5 hours per day on entertainment activities, while studying at home only amounted to 1–2 hours. This situation indicates an imbalance between study time and entertainment media usage, which has the potential to reduce students' learning interest.

Based on these conditions, it can be concluded that low student social studies learning outcomes are not only caused by academic factors alone, but are also closely related to students' learning interests and family support. A less conducive family environment and low learning interests are suspected to be the main factors influencing student learning outcomes. Therefore, a scientific study is needed to determine the extent of the influence of the family environment and learning interests on students' social studies learning outcomes. A deeper understanding of the relationship between these three variables is expected to provide a basis for schools, teachers, and parents in designing more effective learning strategies and mentoring patterns. With synergy between schools and families, it is hoped that students' learning interests will increase, thus positively impacting social studies learning outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning is an indicator of learning success that encompasses cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects, and is influenced by both internal and external factors. One of the most dominant external factors is the family environment, which serves as the primary and primary educational environment for children through parenting, communication, attention, emotional support, and the provision of learning facilities at home. A harmonious and supportive family environment can create a sense of security and psychological comfort, thereby encouraging students' readiness to participate in the learning process. On the other hand, interest in learning is an important internal factor characterized by feelings of joy, attention, active involvement, perseverance, and achievement motivation, which encourage students to learn voluntarily and consistently. Interest in learning does not emerge suddenly, but rather develops through interactions between students and their environment, especially family. Parental support, involvement in learning activities, and positive communication have been shown to increase students' interest in learning. Various previous studies have shown that the family environment directly influences interest in learning, and both together make a significant contribution to learning outcomes. Thus, it can be concluded that a conducive family environment will foster a high interest in learning, which ultimately has a

positive impact on improving student learning outcomes, so that efforts to improve learning achievement need to involve synergy between schools, students, and families.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with a correlational design to analyze the influence of family environment and learning interest on the learning outcomes of ninth-grade students in SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar in the 2025/2026 academic year. The study population was all 319 ninth-grade students, while a sample of 80 students was determined through a proportional random sampling technique. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire to measure family environment and learning interest variables, as well as documentation of Mid-Semester Exam (UTS) scores for the social studies subject as an indicator of learning outcomes. The research instrument was first tested for validity and reliability to ensure its suitability for use. Data analysis was carried out through normality tests, simple and multiple linear regressions, t-tests to determine partial effects, F-tests to determine simultaneous effects, and coefficients of determination to see the contribution of independent variables to the dependent variable. All statistical tests were carried out at a significance level of 5% to obtain accurate conclusions regarding the relationship between family environment, learning interest, and student learning outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

t-test (Partial)

The t test is used to test whether there are independent and dependent variables. The t test in this study is also carried out to find out whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or $\alpha = 5\%$. Then next, we look at the t table $N = 78$ with a significance level of 0.05, the r table value is 1.664. To find out whether the independent variable partially influences the dependent variable, the following t test is carried out:

1. Family Environment (X₁) on Learning Outcomes (Y)

$$r_{xy} = \frac{(80(412368) - (5555)(5976))}{\sqrt{[80(392325) - (5555)^2][80(453696) - (5976)^2]}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{(200,940)}{\sqrt{[31,386,000 - 30,858,025][36,295,680 - 35,712,576]}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{(200,940)}{\sqrt{[527,975][583,104]}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{(200,940)}{\sqrt{(307,912,553,600)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{(200,940)}{554,889}$$

$$r_{xy} = 0.362$$

So the calculation is as follows:

$$t = \frac{0,362\sqrt{80-2}}{\sqrt{1-0,362^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0,362\sqrt{78}}{\sqrt{1-0,131}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,196}{0,932}$$

$$t = 3.43$$

$$r_{xy} = 0.362$$

From the calculation results above, it is known that t count is 3.43 and t table is 1.664.

So $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$, meaning H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It can be concluded that the family environment (X₁) has a significant influence on learning outcomes (Y).

2. Interest in Learning (X₂) Towards Learning Outcomes (Y)

$$r = \frac{n(\sum X_2 Y) - (\sum X_2)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2][n(\sum Y^2) - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{80(453468) - (6050)(5976)}{\sqrt{[80(464014) - (6050)^2][80(453686) - (5976)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{122640}{\sqrt{518620.582304}}$$

$$r = \frac{122640}{\sqrt{549540.2628}}$$

$$r = 0.223$$

So the calculation is as follows:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.223\sqrt{80-2}}{\sqrt{1-0.223^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.223\sqrt{78}}{\sqrt{1-0.0497}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.223(8.8328)}{0.9749}$$

$$t = \frac{1.9707}{0.8749} = 2.022$$

From the calculation results above, it is known that t count is 2,022 and t table is 1.664.

So thitung > tabel, meaning Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. It can be concluded that Learning Interest (X₂) has a significant influence on learning outcomes (Y).

3. Significance Test of Family Environment (X₁) and Interest Study (X₂)

$$r_{1.2} = \frac{n(\sum X_1 X_2) - (\sum X_1)(\sum X_2)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)^2][n(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2]}}$$

$$r_{1.2} = \frac{80(418308) - (5555)(6050)}{\sqrt{[80(392325) - (5555)^2][80(464014) - (6050)^2]}}$$

$$r_{1.2} = \frac{33,464,640 - 33,611,775}{\sqrt{[31,386,000 - 30,858,025] - [37,121,120 - 36,602,500]}}$$

$$r_{1.2} = \frac{147,135}{\sqrt{527,975 - 518,620}}$$

$$r_{1.2} = \frac{147,135}{523,000}$$

$$r_{1.2} = 0.281$$

So the calculation is as follows:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.281\sqrt{80-2}}{\sqrt{1-0.281^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.281\sqrt{78}}{\sqrt{1-0.8328}}$$

$$t = \frac{2.482}{0.9597}$$

$$t = 2.586$$

From the calculation results above, it is known that t count is 2.586 and t table is 1.664. Therefore, t count > t table, meaning that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. It can be concluded that the Family Environment (X₁) does not have a significant influence on Learning Interest (X₂).

4. Test of Significance of Multiple Correlation Coefficient

$$R_{1.2} = \sqrt{\frac{r^2 + r^2 y^2 - 2ry^1 r y^2 r^1.2}{1 - r^2 12}}$$

$$R_{1.2} = \sqrt{\frac{(0,362)^2 + (0,223)(0,281)}{1 - (0,281)^2}}$$

$$R_{1.2} = \sqrt{\frac{0.131044 + 0.062663}{1 - 0.078961}}$$

$$R_{1.2} = \frac{0.193707}{0.921039}$$

$$R_{1.2} = 0.2104$$

To test the closeness of the correlation, it can be tested using the formula:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.2104\sqrt{80-2}}{\sqrt{1-0.2104^2}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.2104\sqrt{78}}{\sqrt{1-8.8328}}$$

$$t = \frac{1.857}{0.9776}$$

$$t = 1.90$$

From the calculation results above, it is known that t count is 1.90 and t table is 1.664. So thitung > ttabel, meaning Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. It can be concluded that the family environment (X₁) Learning interest (X₂) has a significant influence on learning outcomes (Y).

4.2.3.4 f-test (Simultaneous)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, the calculated F is compared with the F table with the condition that if the calculated F > F table then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected. Determining the F table value is to first find the value for the numerator (N1) with the formula: df (N1) = k-1 and for the denominator (N2) namely: df (N2) = nk. So for N1 it is = 3-1 = 2 and for N2 = 80-3 = 77. Then, we look at the F table df for the numerator (N1) = 2 and df for the denominator (N2) = 77 with a significance level of 0.05, the F table value is 3.96 To find out whether the independent variable simultaneously influences the dependent variable, this is done through the F sampling distribution with the formula:

$$F = \frac{JK(\text{reg})/k}{JK-(n-3)}$$

With the statement that:

$$JK(\text{reg}) = b_1 \sum X_1 \cdot y + b_2 \sum X_2 \cdot y$$

$$JK(R) = \sum y^2$$

$$JK(S) = JK(R) - JK(\text{reg})$$

So we get the following:

$$JK(\text{reg}) = (0,032 + (1.39)^2) = 1,598$$

$$JK(R) = 1.460$$

$$JK(S) = 1.598 - 1.460 = 138$$

$$F_{\text{count}} = \frac{1.598/2}{138/80-3}$$

$$F_{\text{count}} = \frac{799}{138/77}$$

$$F_{\text{count}} = 4.463$$

Based on the calculation above, the Fcount value (4.463) > Ftable value (3.96). This shows that the research results reject Ho and accept Ha. Thus, together, the family environment and students' learning interests influence the learning outcomes of class IX students of SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar, with a significant influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that the family environment and students' learning interests simultaneously influence the learning outcome variables in class IX of SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar.

4.2.3.5 Test of Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination test is used to measure the extent to which the family environment and learning interest influence the social studies learning outcomes of class IX students at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar. To measure the percentage value, the coefficient of determination test is carried out as follows:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100\%$$

1. The contribution of the family environment to student learning outcomes obtained data $r = 0.362$ then $r^2 = 0.13104 \times 100\% = 13.104\%$. Thus the influence of the family environment on student learning outcomes is 13.104 and the remainder is 86,896% influenced by other factors.

- The contribution between the variable of learning interest to student learning outcomes obtained data $r = 0.223$ then $r^2 = 0.04973 \times 100\% = 4.973\%$. Thus, the influence of learning interest on student learning outcomes is 4.973% and the remaining 95.027% is influenced by other factors.
- family environment** variables to students' interest in learning is obtained by data $r = 0.281$, then $r^2 = 0.07897 \times 100\% = 7.961\%$. Thus, the influence of interest in learning on students' learning outcomes is 7.961% and the remaining 92.104 % is influenced by other factors.
- The contribution between the variables of **family environment** and learning interest towards student learning outcomes obtained data $r = 0.2104$ then $r^2 = 0.04426 \times 100\% = 4.426\%$. Thus the influence of family environment and learning interest towards student learning outcomes is 4.426% and the remaining 95.574 % is influenced by other factors.

No	Regression	R	r ²	R	100%
1	Y over X ₁	0.362	0.13104		
2	Y over X ₂	0.223	0.04973		
3	X ₁ over X ₂	0.281	0.07897		
4	Y over X ₁ over X ₂			0.210	95,574 %

DISCUSSION

Based on the data analysis that has been carried out, the research process shows the research findings. From the description of the research data, the following data was obtained: To see whether there is a relationship between the variables Y on X₁ and X₂, the magnitude of the multiple linear regression equation is distinguished with the equation $Y = 6.34875 + 0.032 X_1 + 1.39 X_2$, while to see the magnitude of the influence between these variables, it can be seen from the simple correlation test expressed by R. The results of the hypothesis test are:

- There is a positive and significant influence between the family environment on the social studies learning outcomes of grade IX students at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar in the 2025/2026 academic year. This means that if the family environment is sufficient, the students' learning outcomes are sufficient and vice versa. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the influence between the two variables is 0.362, which means that the influence of the family environment is high.
- There is a positive and significant influence between learning interest on the learning outcomes of IX grade students at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar in the 2025/2026 academic year. This means that if learning interest is sufficient then student learning outcomes are sufficient and vice versa. While the magnitude of the influence between the two variables is 0.223 which means that the influence of the family environment is high.
- There is a positive and significant influence between the family environment and learning interest on the learning outcomes of IX grade students at SMP Negeri 4 Pematangsiantar in the 2025/2026 academic year. This means that if the family environment and learning interest are sufficient, the student's learning outcomes are sufficient and vice versa. While the magnitude of the influence between the two variables is 0.281, which means that the influence of the family environment is high.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results as described above in chapter IV, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Where the family environment is declared valid with $r_{count} > r_{table}$ (0.444) and its reliability is declared reliable with $r_{count} (1.007) > Cronbach\ alpha\ value$ (0.6), interest in learning is declared valid with $r_{count} > r_{table}$ (0.444) and its reliability is declared reliable with $r_{count} > (1.031) > Cronbach\ alpha\ value$ (0.6).
- Simple linear regression test for family environment $Y = 77,30 + 0,032 X_1$ means that if the family environment (X₁) is higher, the learning outcomes are also higher and simple linear regression test for learning interest $Y = 59.1 + 1.39 X_2$ means that if (X₂) is higher, the learning outcomes are also higher.
- Multiple regression test for family environment and learning interest on student learning outcomes $Y = 6.34875 + 0.032 X_1 + 1.39 X_2$ which means that if the availability of family environment and learning interest both have an influence on student learning outcomes
- The partial test (t-test) for the family environment with student learning outcomes was declared significant with $t_{count} (2.022) > t_{table} (1.664)$, for learning interest with student learning outcomes where $t_{count} (1.90) > t_{table} (1.664)$.
- The simultaneous test (F test) for X₁ and X₂ with Y was declared significant with $F_{count} (4.463) > F_{table} (3.96)$.

6. The coefficient of determination test for the availability of learning resources and learning interest on student learning outcomes obtained data $r^2 \times 100\% = 95.574\%$ which means significant.

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